

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ АУТЕНТИЧНЫХ ВИДЕОРОЛИКОВ В ОБУЧЕНИИ ГОВОРЕНИЮ НА УРОКАХ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

THE USE OF AUTHENTIC VIDEOS IN TEACHING SPEAKING AT THE ENGLISH LESSONS

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В данной статье представлено комплексное описание использования аутентичных видеоматериалов на уроках английского языка для развития навыков говорения у учащихся старших классов. Авторами данного исследования описан педагогический опыт работы с видеороликами на уроках английского языка. В результате проведенного исследования установлено что, методически верное применение аутентичных видеоматериалов в учебном процессе способствует развитию навыков говорения у учащихся, повышению интереса к изучению иностранного языка, развитию самостоятельности, креативности и познавательной активности учащихся. Полученные результаты доказали эффективность применения видео в практике обучения данному учебному предмету.

This article presents a comprehensive description of the use of authentic video materials in English lessons for the development of speaking skills in high school students. The authors of this study describe the pedagogical experience of working with videos in English lessons. As a result of the conducted research, it was found that the methodically correct use of authentic video materials in the educational process contributes to the development of students' speaking skills, increased interest in learning a foreign language, the development of independence, creativity and cognitive activity of students. The obtained results proved the effectiveness of the use of video in the practice of teaching this academic subject.

Ключевые слова: учебная деятельность, урок английского языка, навыки говорения, аутентичные видеоматериалы, педагогическая технология, метод проектов, учебный проект, мотивация.

Key words: *educational activity, English lesson, speaking skills, authentic video materials, pedagogical technology, project method, educational project, motivation.*

As you know, the formation of speaking skills is one of the most important conditions in learning a foreign language. Learning to speak includes the formation of dialogic and monologue speech skills, as well as the perception and understanding of sounding speech. One of the ways to form and further develop speaking skills is to use authentic videos in the learning process. Authentic video material is video recordings intended for native speakers (combining visual and sound series), which contain linguistic and extralinguistic information of the spheres of society's life related to the professional activities of future specialists, and showing the functioning of language as a means of professional communication in a natural environment [7, p. 149]. Video is a valuable educational resource, because thanks to video, you can create a real foreign language environment that promotes better understanding, reflects the behavior of interlocutors, enriches students' experience in communication, creates realistic models for situational exercises and role-playing games, enriches students' knowledge. Video materials increase the activity of students, they are immersed in a natural foreign language environment, they have a desire to express their opinion on what they see, which contributes to the development of communication skills in a foreign language, and it is the main goal of teaching a foreign language. Authentic materials contain linguistic and cultural information, provide an opportunity to simulate communicative situations and involve students in the process of communication in a foreign language.

Taking into account the foregoing, the relevance of this study lies in the fact that the use of authentic video materials is one of the most effective ways to form and develop speaking skills, which explains the need for this study.

The problem of this study is to find the effectiveness of the formation of speaking skills with the help of authentic videos in English lessons.

The issue of the introduction and subsequent use of authentic video materials in the educational process was dealt with by many theoreticians and practitioners. Thus, the influence of video materials on the formation of sociocultural competence can be traced in the works of Azimov E.G. [1], Gvozdeva A.S. [3], Kirillova N.B. [5] In the works of Nagovitsyna O.V. [8], Klimova G.S., Svetova E.A. [6], Kamardina Yu.S. [4], Verisokina Yu.I. [2] developments on the introduction of video into the educational process are presented. Soboleva A.V. [10], Sergeeva N.N. [9] note the huge potential of video materials in shaping the motivation to learn a foreign language.

The introduction of authentic video materials for the development of speaking skills has an undeniable advantage. They contain the most communicatively meaningful lexical units that are typical for everyday situations of communication. First of all, these are various clichés, vocabulary for defending one's point of view, background and non-equivalent vocabulary, words that have a socio-cultural or national-cultural component. Authentic texts that are contained in video visualization also have their own grammatical style: the use of abbreviations, omissions of inserts. which are characteristic of authentic live communication [7]. The video material has communicative integrity, thanks to which it meets the cognitive and emotional needs of students, activates their mental activity. Video materials offer students already developed speech patterns of communication by native speakers, which helps to form speaking skills in a foreign language.

As part of experimental and diagnostic training, we studied the influence of authentic video materials on the formation of speaking skills of 10th grade students.

Experimental diagnostic training consisted of three stages:

The first stage is ascertaining. At this stage, the primary diagnostics of speaking skills was carried out.

The second stage is formative. At this stage, classes were conducted using authentic videos aimed at developing students' speaking skills.

The third stage is control. At this stage, a repeated diagnosis of the students' speaking skills was carried out, as well as an analysis of the results obtained.

At the first stage, the students were offered a conversation on the studied topic "Hobbies and past times". The analysis of the results showed that the majority of students experienced difficulties in constructing sentences and using vocabulary corresponding to the topic.

The first stage of experimental diagnostic training showed that it is necessary to carry out the next, formative stage, which involves the inclusion of authentic videos in the structure of English lessons in order to form students' speaking skills. In the control group, English lessons were conducted in the usual educational mode, and in the experimental group, the lessons were conducted with the maximum use of authentic video materials.

When selecting videos, the following criteria were taken into account:

- clarity of sound and picture
- selection of the necessary video fragment on the topic, in which there will be the necessary amount of feasible language material
- speech clarity, speed and accent
- compliance with the level of communicative competence of students, their interests and needs;
- observance of natural pauses between statements;
- slang expressions and exclamations should be relatively short and not too difficult to understand;
- video duration is no more than 5 minutes.

Authentic video materials were selected in accordance with the curriculum. For more effective work with video materials, exercises were developed that helped not only to form speaking skills, but also to learn new lexical units and grammatical constructions.

Work with each of the videos included three stages:

- Pre-demonstration - acquaintance with new lexical units from videos and tasks to be completed after watching the video
- Demo - view video
- Post-demonstration - performing tasks aimed at developing speaking skills (answering questions, compiling dialogues, expressing one's opinion using supports)

After conducting lessons using authentic videos, the control phase of the study was implemented.

The purpose of the control stage: to identify the effectiveness of the experimental diagnostic training.

At this stage, a repeated diagnosis of the development of speaking skills was carried out. The students were offered a questionnaire on the topics studied with the help of video materials, as well as a description of the photographs.

The results of the control stage showed that the students completed the tasks more confidently, made fewer grammatical errors, and the speech contained the lexical units studied while working on the video.

Thus, the conducted experimental diagnostic training aimed at developing speaking skills with the help of authentic video materials has proved its effectiveness. Their use in the educational process also motivates students to further study a foreign language. The use of a set of exercises for working on video helps to make the learning process interesting and varied.

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